

SOLVING HIDDEN HUNGER: CONTRIBUTIONS OF VARIOUS SECTORS – A Review

**Snigdha Priyadarshini¹, Rachna V¹, Janmey Taral Shah¹,
DJ Mukesh Kumar², Aadil Ahmed Irshath and Anand Prem Rajan^{1*}**

¹Department of Biotechnology, School of Bio Sciences and Technology (SBST) Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Vellore – 632014, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Environmental Science Division, Centre for Research, Bharath Institute of Science and Technology (BIHER) Selaiyur. Chennai 600073, Tamil Nadu, India.

***Corresponding Author:**

Dr Anand Prem Rajan

Professor

School of Bio Sciences and Technology (SBST)

Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT),

Vellore, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Hidden hunger is a widespread problem in developing countries, characterized by a lack of essential vitamins and minerals in the diet, despite adequate calorie intake. The effects of hidden hunger are severe, including stunted growth, weakened immune systems, and increased risk of disease and death. The primary causes of hidden hunger include poverty, food insecurity, and a lack of access to diverse and nutritious foods. Reliance on staple crops can lead to a lack of essential nutrients in the diet. Governments and international organizations have implemented various interventions to address hidden hunger, including fortification of staple foods with micronutrients, dietary diversification programs, and targeted supplementation. However, these efforts have faced challenges such as limited access to fortified foods, lack of behavioral change communication, and inadequate monitoring and evaluation. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the problem of hidden hunger, as supply chain disruptions and economic hardship have reduced access to nutritious foods. The pandemic has also highlighted the need for more resilient and sustainable food systems. To effectively address hidden hunger, it is crucial to address the underlying causes, including poverty and food insecurity. Interventions must be culturally appropriate and targeted to specific populations in need. In addition, the impact of these interventions must be closely monitored and evaluated to ensure their effectiveness. In this paper, we present a review of the multifaceted problems stemming from hidden hunger and solutions taken against these problems and their effectiveness.

KEYWORDS: Hidden hunger, micronutrients, social enterprises, public sector, Non-Governmental Organisations, Private sector

1. INTRODUCTION:

Lack of appropriate intake of bioavailable minerals and vitamins from the basic meals is the main cause of micronutrient deficiencies. This problem is made worse by the large levels of inhibitors and low levels of enhancers of vitamin absorption found in many regularly consumed foods and beverages (such as rice, wheat, corn, legumes, tea, and coffee)(Lowe, 2021). In underdeveloped countries, efforts to secure the world's food supply and uplift populations from starvation and severe food scarcity have been underway for a long time. However there exist several populations of people susceptible to micronutrient deficiency, despite their surface level food security (Gödecke et al., 2018)(Stein & Qaim, 2007). This may be due to poor quality of food that which contains the necessary calories but lacking in essential nutrients that support growth, such as iodine, iron, zinc and vitamins.

Micronutrient	Symptoms of Deficiency	At risk populations	Reference
Iodine	Weak immune system, Goitre, Cretinism (in children)	Women of reproductive age, BIPOC.	(Hatch-McChesney & Lieberman, 2022)
Iron	Anaemia, fatigue, weakness, palpitations	Infants, pregnant women, children	(Camaschella, 2019)
Zinc	Hair loss, skin lesions, dwarfism	Children, elderly population	(Hambidge, 2000)
Vitamin A	Xerophthalmia, susceptibility to illness, growth disorders	Preschool age children, pregnant women	(WHO Global Database on Vitamin A Deficiency, 2009)
Vitamin C	Scurvy, poor wound healing	Elderly, men	(Ravindran et al., 2011)
Vitamin B	Macrocytic anaemia, dementia, neurological disorders	Elderly	(ROBERT & BROWN, 2003)
Vitamin E	Fat malabsorption, myopathy, ataxia	Children	(Dror & Allen, 2011)
Vitamin D	Rickets, osteomalacia	Children of underdeveloped countries	(Prentice, 2008)

Table 1. Micronutrient deficiencies and prevalent populations

Approaches to solving hidden hunger at a macro level have primarily involved food fortification efforts (Jiang et al., 2021). Food fortification is not a new nutritional intervention. Post World War II, fortification with a range of nutrients became common in the United States and some parts of Europe. Food fortification was a key factor in eliminating rickets (vitamin D in milk), goitre (iodine in salt) and pellagra (niacin fortification of cereals and other grains) and has also been effective in reducing the incidence of iron deficiency (Murgia et al., 2012). Worldwide, fortification of salt with iodine has produced major reductions in iodine deficiency disorders (Zimmermann, 2004). However, with the exception of iodine in salt, food fortification has not yet been used

more extensively in developing countries. Fortification as a nutrition intervention offers clear advantages in that foods commonly consumed can be fortified without requiring changes in consumption behaviour on the part of the consumer. The costs of fortification are modest and a variety of technologies now exist.

Food fortification efforts need to be integrated within the context of a country's public health and nutrition situation and as part of an overall micronutrient strategy that uses other interventions as well. Effective and sustainable fortification will be possible only if the public sector (that has the mandate and responsibility to improve the health of population), the private sector (that has experience and expertise in food production and marketing) and the social sector (that has the grass-roots contact with the consumer) collaborate to develop, produce and promote micronutrient fortified foods.

Figure 1. Problems leading to hidden hunger

2. CONTRIBUTION OF BIOTECHNOLOGY TO SOLVING HIDDEN HUNGER

The fields of Agriculture and Plant science have contributed greatly toward understanding the limitations and the various ways in which crops can be improved, both in yield and nutrition content. Using genetic engineering approaches, biotechnologists have fortified certain varieties of crops to increase the production or accumulation of a particular nutrient, thus ensuring that consumption of such plants on a regular basis would act as a preventative method against micronutrient deficiency.

S.no	Crop	Modification	Benefits	Reference
1.	Golden Rice	Inclusion of gene producing beta carotene	Beta carotene is a precursor of Vitamin A, which is essential for prevention of night blindness	(Tang et al., 2009)
2.	Tomato	accumulation of provitamin D3	Vitamin D is essential for skeletal development and steroid hormone activity	(Li et al., 2022)
3.	Maize	Accumulation of Iron	Prevention of anaemia, increased immunity due to greater iron content	(Lung'aho et al., 2011)
4.	Mustard	Zinc biofortification	Increased uptake of zinc ensures vital to neuro behavioural health and immunity.	(Di Gioia et al., 2019)

Table 2. Contributions of biotechnology toward reducing micronutrient deficiency

3. CONTRIBUTION OF THE PUBLIC SECTOR

The public sector plays a vital role in addressing hidden hunger. Some of the ways that the public sector contributes to solving hidden hunger include policy and regulation, investment in agriculture, nutrition education, and food assistance programs, healthcare (Eggersdorfer & Bird, 2016). The government can create policies and regulations aimed at promoting access to nutritious food, such as fortifying staple foods with essential vitamins and minerals (Maberly et al., 2003). The public sector can invest in agriculture to support the production of nutritious foods, including fruits and vegetables that can help to address hidden hunger. They can also provide nutrition education to communities to raise awareness about the importance of a balanced and nutritious diet (Latham, M. C., 2003). The government can provide food assistance programs, such as food stamps and school meal programs, to ensure that families and children have access to nutritious food. They can also provide access to health care services, such as prenatal care and nutrition counselling, to prevent and treat malnutrition (Hoddinott et al., 2016). The Indian government launched a multi-ministerial convergence scheme called the Poshan Abhiyaan to tackle malnutrition, including hidden hunger, among children, pregnant women, and lactating mothers. Operation Flood in India was a dairy development program that aimed to increase milk production and distribution in India. The program helped to improve the dietary diversity of vulnerable populations and address hidden hunger.

3.1. POSHAN ABHIYAAN IN INDIA

Abhiyaan, which focuses on the nutritional status of adolescent girls, pregnant women, breastfeeding moms, and children 0–6 years old, was formally launched on March 8th, 2018 in the Jhunjhunu district of Rajasthan. The initiative sought to eliminate stunting, nutrient deficiencies, anaemia, and low birth weight in children, tackling malnutrition at a young age through the use of technology, collaboration, and community action (Puri & Mehlawat, 2022).

Source: Ministry of Women and child Development, <http://dashboard.poshanabhiyaan.gov.in/janandolan/#/>

Figure 2. Statistics of Demographics aided by Poshan Abhiyaan (Child Development, Poshan Abhiyaan 2020)

The POSHAN Abhiyaan programme, which stands for the Prime Minister's Overarching Plan for Holistic Nutrition, is a cross-ministerial project with the tagline "Jan Andolan," which translates to "people's movement." (Misra et al., 2020). The Abhiyaan wants everyone in the country to have the battle against malnutrition as their top priority. A total of 2.51 billion people have participated in the programme so far, taking part in more than 3644 million events. The National Nutrition Mission's goal is to reduce stunting from 38.4% to 25% by 2022, as stated in "Mission 25 by 2020" (Suri & Kapur, 2020).

In addition to conducting social audits, the mission includes mapping numerous other malnutrition-related programmes and enabling synergies through ICT-based real-time monitoring systems, robust convergence between programmes, rewarding states and UTs for meeting their goals, and optimising the operation of Anganwadi centres.

The progress report for POSHAN Abhiyaan for the period of October 2019 to April 2020 examines the organization's current situation and the difficulties it has had in implementing its plans on various levels. According to the findings, better complementary feeding through behavioural modification can prevent 60% of all cases of stunting (Kapur & Suri, 2020).

3.2. OPERATION FLOOD IN INDIA

Operation Flood, which was started in 1970, has assisted dairy farmers in managing their own development and taking ownership of the resources they produce. A National Milk Grid connects customers in more than 700 towns and cities with milk farmers across India, minimising seasonal and regional price differences while ensuring that the producer consistently receives fair market rates in a transparent manner. (Doornbos et al., 1987) Village milk producers' cooperatives, which purchase milk, offer inputs and services, and give members access to contemporary management and technology, have formed the foundation of Operation Flood. The goals of Operation Flood are to Increase your milk output ("a flood of milk"), to increase rural incomes and to provide affordable costs for customers (Terhal & Doornbos, 1983).

Phase I, from 1970 and 1980, was funded by the sale of butter oil and skim milk powder that had been donated by the European Union, then the EEC, via the World Food Programme. The EEC support was negotiated and the programme was planned by NDDB. Operation Flood's first phase involved connecting consumers in India's four largest metropolises—Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, and Chennai—with 18 of the best milksheds in the country.

In Phase II of Operation Flood (1981–1985), the number of milksheds rose from 18 to 136, and the number of milk outlets climbed to 290 urban markets. A self-sustaining network of 43,000 village cooperatives serving 4.25 million milk producers had been established by the end of 1985. Domestic milk powder production climbed from 22,000 tonnes in the year before the operation to 140,000 tonnes in 1989, with dairies established as part of Operation Flood accounting for the entire increase. In this way, loans from the World Bank and gifts from the EEC supported independence. Producers' cooperatives increased their direct milk marketing by several million litres per day.

Phase III (1985–1996) allowed dairy cooperatives to develop and expand the infrastructure needed to obtain and market rising milk volumes. For cooperative members, services for feed, artificial insemination, and veterinary first aid were expanded, and member education was enhanced. Phase III of Operation Flood strengthened India's dairy cooperative movement by establishing 30,000 new cooperatives in addition to the 42,000 societies that had already been set up during Phase II. As the number of women members and Women's Dairy Cooperative Societies increased dramatically, milksheds reached a peak of 173 in 1988–1989 at that time. In Phase III, research and development in animal nutrition and health received more attention. Developments like the Theileriosis vaccine, bypass protein diet, and urea-molasses mineral blocks all helped milch animals produce more milk (Atkins, 1988). Dairying was now viewed as a tool for development, providing millions of rural residents with stable jobs and money (*Operation Flood: Dairy Development in India on JSTOR*, n.d.).

Year	Production (Million tonnes)	Per Capita Availability (gms/day)
1991-92	55.6	178
1992-93	58.0	182
1993-94	60.6	186
1994-95	63.8	192
1995-96	66.2	195
1996-97	69.1	200
1997-98	72.1	205
1998-99	75.4	210
1999-2K	78.3	214
2000-01	80.6	217
2001-02	84.4	222
2002-03	86.2	224
2003-04	88.1	225
2004-05	92.5	233
2005-06	97.1	241
2006-07	102.6	251
2007-08	107.9	260
2008-09	112.2	266
2009-10	116.4	273
2010-11	121.8	281
2011-12	127.9	290
2012-13	132.4	299
2013-14	137.7	307
2014-15	146.3	322
2015-16	155.5	337
2016-17	165.4	355
2017-18	176.3	375
2018-19	187.7	394
2019-20	198.4	406

Source: Basic Animal Husbandry Statistics, DAHD&F, GoI

Figure 3. Increase in milk production due to operation flood in India (Basic Animal Husbandry Statistics, DAHD&F, GoI, 2020)

4. CONTRIBUTION OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR

The private sector also plays a significant role in solving hidden hunger. Some of the ways that the private sector contributes include food fortification, investment in agriculture, research and development, marketing and education and other social responsibility initiatives.

Private companies can fortify their food products with essential vitamins and minerals to help address hidden hunger. They can invest in agriculture to support the production of nutritious foods, including fruits and vegetables, that can help to address hidden hunger. They can also engage in research and development to find innovative solutions to hidden hunger, such as new food fortification techniques or the development of biofortified crops. They can use marketing and education to raise awareness about the importance of a balanced and nutritious diet, and to promote their nutritious food products. They can also take a leadership role in addressing hidden hunger through social responsibility initiatives, such as partnering with NGOs to provide food assistance to communities in need (Detzel & KlassecnWigger, 2020).

The private sector has a significant role to play in addressing hidden hunger, both through its business operations and through its corporate social responsibility initiatives. By leveraging its resources and expertise, the private sector can help to ensure that everyone has access to the essential vitamins and minerals they need to lead healthy and productive lives.

Nestlé is a Swiss multinational food and beverage company that has been fortifying its products with essential vitamins and minerals in many countries, including India, where it launched a range of fortified Maggi noodles to address hidden hunger among children (Nestle, 2017).

Unilever, a British-Dutch multinational consumer goods company, has been fortifying its products in many countries, including India, where it launched a range of fortified foods, such as cooking oil and salt, to address hidden hunger. This was done in partnership with the World Food Programme focussed in countries like South Sudan, Haiti and Indonesia (Unilever, 2020).

PepsiCo, an American multinational food and beverage company, has been working with small-scale farmers in many countries, including India, to promote the production of nutritious foods, such as fruits and vegetables, and to improve the livelihoods of farmers.

4.1. NESTLE

Nestle's regionally tailored Popularly Positioned Products (PPPs) offer low-income consumers nutritious goods at a reasonable cost and the right serving size. They created a lot of fortified Popularly Positioned Products, which are high-quality foods and drinks with nutritious content at a cost that lower-income consumers can afford (Nestle, 2017).

In 2020, under the “Simply Good” Initiative- Nestle released iron fortified instant noodles, making it publicly available at the same cost as their commercial noodles in order to incentivize buying of the same. This was done specifically in the Indian subcontinent to address chronic iron deficiency. This is particularly common in rural India. Besides this, they decreased sodium and MSG content in their product. The popularity of ‘Maggi’ noodles multiplies the beneficial impact intended. This is because ‘Maggi’ has become a household brand- about 2.5 million portions are consumed by Indians, consumed by approximately 33% of all families across multiple varied communities (Nestle, 2020).

The iron fortified noodles were created to satiate 15% of the recommended dietary intake of iron. This was an important step and its impact was found to directly influence marginalized communities- Maggi is a cheap, easily accessible snack. Usually, foods with plenty of iron content are fresh foods- fresh foods are prone to quick spoilage and need to be consumed fast, so they are sparingly bought by consumers. These foods are also sparsely sold during off season. More importantly, other sources including superfoods like chia seeds are expensive. This makes Nestle an important platform for outreach (Nestle, 2020).

Additionally, Nestle has also fortified popular Maggi dishes like seasonings, soups and noodles with iodine as well. This is commensurate with government standards of iodized salt. This is also a significant step as one of the most widespread micronutrient deficiencies, impacting two billion people worldwide, is inadequate dietary iodine. The main factor causing reversible brain injury is iodine deficiency. Iodine shortage in severe forms during pregnancy might cause miscarriage or new-born mental impairment (Nestle, 2020).

These products have created a positive cycling influence as illustrated in Figure 4, developments like these have improved market penetration among consumers with lower incomes by 30–40%, and they are a major reason why Maggi noodles are now more widely available in small towns.

4.2. UNILEVER:

Unilever is a multinational corporation that has pledged to take multifaceted approaches to issues of food insecurity. A staggering and growing issue is that of food waste.

One-third of all food produced worldwide is lost or wasted, creating a global issue of food loss and waste. According to the UN Environment Programme, this equates to nearly 1.3 billion tonnes of food, which would require more land surface area than both China and India put together. Addressing food insecurity, preserving natural resources, and reducing climate change can all be accomplished by addressing food waste, but this requires a worldwide strategy. Nobody should have to deal with hunger and malnutrition on a daily basis, especially in light of the fact that every day, billions of kilograms of nutritious food are wasted (Unilever, 2023).

Unilever has set out well defined goals to tackle this problem as well. They want to reduce food waste in their direct operations from the plant to the shelf by 50% by the year 2025. They employ manufacturing improvements and circular economy ideas as food-saving strategies. For instance, rather than allowing the ice cream to go to waste when the ice cream packing lines break, they keep it safely until the lines can be repaired. In order to prevent waste, they also make sure to utilize every scrap of raw materials. Additionally, they regularly update and publicize a global report every year on the food wastage caused across the Unilever infrastructure. This move ensures transparency (Unilever, 2023).

The Unilever brand Knorr is actively encouraging people to use their creativity when it comes to food. Through its #EatForGood campaign, which promotes thoughtful eating, Knorr has raised awareness about the value of minimizing food waste, beginning in the kitchen. It also supports sustainable agriculture (Unilever, 2020).

Unilever also instructs their consumers with guidelines on how to prevent food waste through their packaging materials. This move increases consumer awareness. These instructions range from preventing consumers from buying excess food, urging them to plan their meals and prepare detailed shopping lists such that they don't

overbuy. These also include encouraging consumers to make compost heaps, turning kitchen scraps into fertilizer, and storing food correctly (Unilever, 2020).

Figure 5. Excerpt from 2020 Unilever Report on Food Waste (Global Unilever Food Waste Report, 2020.)

4.3. PEPSICO:

To create products that offer nutritional advantages, PepsiCo is consistently developing and growing its portfolio. While decreasing added sugars, sodium, and saturated fat in many of our products, they are also investing in innovation to supply key food categories and nutrients that support a balanced diet, accelerating a path we started before the turn of the twenty-first century. (Alexander, 2011)

Through a combination of product innovation, reformulation, and brand acquisition throughout the years, they have widened their portfolio:

Through reformulations, they have lower added sugars, salt, and saturated fat in many of their products, enhancing their nutritional profiles. Product innovations support their portfolio by satisfying regional market preferences and tastes while giving consumers the nourishment they need. They have expanded their company by acquiring some of the most reputable and well-liked positive nutrition brands in the globe.

They use the PepsiCo Nutrition Criteria to help provide nutrition guidelines during the creation of beverages and snacks and broaden their product line (PNC). The World Health Organization (WHO), the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA), the National Academy of Medicine, and national public health authorities are just a few of the top international and national nutrition authorities who have recommended foods and nutrient intake on which these science-based standards are based. (Pepsico, 2016). Based on the most recent scientific findings and dietary recommendations relevant to each country, the PNC established standards for nutrients to limit as well as nutrients and food groups to encourage.

In the top 23 markets, PepsiCo produces around 7 million tonnes of easy food, which accounts for 86% of total food sales. In their top 26 markets, they sell beverage products totalling over 650 million hectolitres (79% of

total beverage sales volume). PepsiCo continues to work towards its aim of good nutrition through a combination of product updates, innovations, and acquisitions. (Pepsico, 2019). In the top 26 beverage markets, 53% of the sales volume of the beverage portfolio did not exceed 100 calories from added sugars per 12-ounce serving; In the top 23 beverage markets, 66% of the sales volume of the portfolio of convenient foods did not exceed 1.3 mg of sodium per calorie; In the top 23 beverage markets, 75% of the sales volume of the portfolio of convenient foods did not exceed 1.1g of saturated fat per 100 calories.

Added Sugars	10% of total energy contribution	Total sugars ≤ 4.5g/100g*	0g - 7g/100ml*
Sodium	< 5g salt (equals < 1.966g sodium)	≤ 400mg / 100g**	1.0mg - 1.6 mg/kcal**
Saturated Fat	< 10% of total energy contribution***	≤ 6.0g/ 100g**	0.8g- 1.7 g/100 kcal**

*Beverages Category (for PepsiCo criterion assuming 1cc liquid weighs 1g)
 **Snacks Category (for PepsiCo criterion assuming typical serving size of 28g serving)
 ***Based on 2,000kcal diet = 22g per day of sat fat

Figure 6. Excerpt from Pepsico Report 2019 of how PNC compares to other standards (PepsiCo Nutrition Criteria, 2019)

5. CONTRIBUTION OF NGOS:

NGOs play a critical role in addressing hidden hunger by providing community-based solutions, advocating for policy change, and delivering essential services and support to communities in need. Through their work, NGOs help to ensure that everyone has access to the essential vitamins and minerals they need to lead healthy and productive lives. Some of the ways that NGOs contribute include community outreach, food assistance programs, agriculture and livelihoods, healthcare, advocacy and policy change.

NGOs can reach out to communities and educate them about the importance of a balanced and nutritious diet, as well as the ways in which they can access and afford nutritious food. They can provide food assistance programs, such as food banks and soup kitchens, to ensure that families and children have access to nutritious food. They can also work with small-scale farmers to improve their agricultural practices and provide them with the resources they need to grow and sell nutritious foods, such as fruits and vegetables. They can also provide access to health care services, such as prenatal care and nutrition counselling, to prevent and treat malnutrition. They can advocate for policy changes that support access to nutritious food, such as food fortification laws, and work to raise awareness about the importance of addressing hidden hunger.

There are many NGOs working to address hidden hunger around the world. These organizations play an important role in complementing the efforts of governments and other stakeholders to improve nutritional outcomes and reduce the negative impacts of hidden hunger. HarvestPlus is an international NGO that works to breed biofortified crops and promote their adoption to improve nutrition and combat hidden hunger in developing countries.

Project Peanut Butter is an NGO that provides ready-to-use therapeutic food to children suffering from severe acute malnutrition, including those affected by hidden hunger, in developing countries.

5.1. HARVESTPLUS:

HarvestPlus is a nationwide non-governmental organization that works to support farmers' hands on. It supports organizations that help agricultural households get biofortified planting material, comprehend its agronomic and nutritional advantages, learn how to grow biofortified crops, and get the necessary technical support.

Depending on the type of crop and the local or national market context, different channels are used to deliver planting materials and other inputs to farmers (Lyons et al., 2004), such as fertilizer, by Business channels (i.e. seed companies and agro-dealers), Programs or divisions of government, Nongovernmental and charitable groups, Direct exchange of planting materials between farmers

Additionally, farming households are given information on the fundamentals of nutrition as well as the nutritional value of biofortified crops, how to raise them, and how to prepare foods using them. Women make up over two thirds of the farmers trained by HarvestPlus and its affiliates (Fairweather-Tait et al., 2013).

Moreover, they have laid expansion plans to scale up lending access to biofortified crops. They have a five-pronged setup. They have a five-pronged setup. The first prong is the evidence base. They aim to extend and disseminate study findings on the health and nutritional benefits, as well as proof of a beneficial effect on farming families, consumers, and value chain participants. The second prong is environment for policy. They promote national, regional, and global policies and activities that support biofortification. Integrating biofortification into public support programmes is a top goal. The third prong is Market incentives. They promote traceability and certification methods, financing mechanisms, and standards for biofortified products to give value chain participants clarity and reduce market risk. The fourth prong is Strengthening of capacity. They ensure that all partners involved in biofortification including those involved in value chains, farmer participation, crop re-research and development, and nutrition/impact research are capable of acting independently and efficiently. The final prong is Knowledge sharing. They consistently record facts, knowledge, and lessons learnt and communicate them broadly via various media.

Figure 7. HarvestPlus model (Bouis & Saltzman, 2017)

5.2. PROJECT PEANUT BUTTER

Project Peanut Butter (PPB) aims to improve the use of efficient, locally produced ready-to-use therapeutic foods in the treatment of severe malnutrition, which is currently the leading cause of child mortality worldwide. In order to help children in sub-Saharan Africa and elsewhere who are very acutely malnourished, this charitable organization was created.

Dr. Manary and his colleague Dr. André Briend experimented with several ingredients between 2000 and 2004 until they developed a recipe that offers the precise, superior nutrition that extremely malnourished youngsters require to recover. The dish was later referred to as Ready-to-Use Therapeutic Food (RUTF). RUTF is a peanut butter-like paste that is high in energy but contains other ingredients. It contains sugar, vegetable oil, roasted ground peanuts (peanut paste), powdered milk, vitamins, and minerals. Peanuts are high in protein and zinc, which is healthy for the immune system (Global Health Centre, 2016).

They also include monounsaturated fats, which are simple to digest. The target audience for RUTF is severely underweight kids between the ages of 6 months and 5 years. For a number of reasons, feeding kids RUTF at home was a groundbreaking therapy. Before RUTF, moms had to bring their sick children to congested hospitals or clinics where they got milk-based formula as the standard treatment for malnourished infants. Recovery rates were only 25–40%, but 75–95% for RUTF-based home-based treatment (Andersson, 2017).

Figure 8. Composition of RUTF(Andersson et al., 2017)

RUTF is created locally, in the nations where the product is required. The project employs as many locally sourced ingredients as possible, which is one of the most distinctive parts of Project Peanut Butter's work. The projects create jobs for farmers, manufacturing employees, administrators, nurses, health assistants, drivers, and other professionals, boosting local economies and fostering stronger communities. Furthermore, carbon impact is reduced by obtaining a large portion of raw materials locally. Selecting local production guarantees that healthcare systems in vulnerable communities will always have access to RUTF supplies. Importing RUTF can frequently be difficult due to issues including shipment delays and goods being delayed in ports because of exorbitant customs fines.

Because of the long-standing history of local manufacturing in poor countries and the founder's substantial experience in the field of malnutrition research, Project Peanut Butter has a significant amount of knowledge and competence about RUTF production. To help more kids who require therapy, they try to whenever feasible to share this information with other organisations. As a result, in addition to sustaining their own continuing operations, they have funded other small-scale industrial projects in Africa and elsewhere (Global Health Centre, 2016).

Project Peanut Butter in Sierra Leone (PPB Sierra Leone) started a new maternal health research for moms who are undernourished in March 2017. The trial enrolls malnourished pregnant women who are up to 35 weeks pregnant in a programme that distributes Mama Dutasi, a ready-to-use supplementary meal (RUSF). Iron and folic acid, among other essential nutrients and vitamins for a healthy pregnancy, are provided by Mama Dutasi. The women also receive deworming treatments, infection screenings, malaria prevention advice, and genital urethritis testing. Once the baby is born, the ladies visit a PPB clinic every two weeks. The goal of PPB researchers is to draw the conclusion that effective prenatal care will result in newborns who are healthier and less stunted even after birth (Projectpb, 2018).

6. CONTRIBUTION OF SOCIAL ENTREPRISES:

Social enterprises play a critical role in addressing hidden hunger by using business as a force for good. By leveraging their innovation, entrepreneurship, and social impact focus, social enterprises can create new solutions and opportunities that help to ensure that everyone has access to the essential vitamins and minerals they need to lead healthy and productive lives.

Some of the ways that social enterprises contribute includes innovative business models, food fortification, and employment quo challenge along with income generation and environmental stability.

Social enterprises can use innovative business models to provide access to nutritious food, such as community-supported agriculture programs that connect consumers directly with local farmers. Social enterprises can fortify their food products with essential vitamins and minerals to help address hidden hunger. Social enterprises can challenge the status quo by creating new products, services, and markets that make nutritious food more accessible and affordable, especially in underserved communities. They can also create employment and income-generating opportunities, especially for small-scale farmers and rural communities, to improve their access to nutritious food. They can also work to promote environmental sustainability in their operations and supply chains, which can help to ensure a long-term supply of nutritious food. Here are a few examples of the many social enterprises working to address hidden hunger around the world. These organizations use innovative business models to create positive social and environmental impact while generating financial returns.

One Acre Fund is a social enterprise that provides smallholder farmers in Africa with access to finance, seed, and training to grow nutritious food, including biofortified crops. Nourish the Children is a social enterprise that operates a direct-selling model to distribute nutrient-rich food products to families in need, helping to address hidden hunger and improve nutritional outcomes.

6.1. ONE ACRE FUND:

More than 50 million families in Sub-Saharan Africa earn a living from small farms, which produce 80 percent of the continent's food. (Impact of Interventions by One Acre Fund, 2018). According to the report, these farmers have lower harvests compared to the rest of the world. One Acre Fund provides the financing and training needed to increase their yields and profits, instead of giving handouts. (Impact of Interventions by One Acre Fund, 2018). By investing in farmers, they help them grow their way out of hunger and build lasting pathways to prosperity. When farmers become more productive, they contribute to feeding healthy communities and creating thriving economies. (Impact of Interventions by One Acre Fund, 2018). Additionally, by doing more with less land, they reduce environmental pressure.

One Acre Fund started in 2006 with a pilot group of 38 farmers in Kenya. Over the years, they have served more than 3 million farmers both directly and indirectly. (Impact of Interventions by One Acre Fund, 2018). The organization aims to put more income in farmers' pockets for every dollar they spend, which is called "social return on investment" or SROI. In 2021, One Acre Fund served farmers that produced \$3.60 in new income and assets for every \$1 donated. (Impact of Interventions by One Acre Fund, 2018). They are able to

work with the farmers and also provide quality farm products on credit, which farmers repay over the full growing season. They deliver these products within walking distance of farmers’ homes, in time for planting. They train farmers on effective agricultural practices and how to sell any harvest sur-plus.

By 2030, they aim to serve 10 million farmers fully 10 percent of the families in the world living on \$1 a day. In 2021, they have currently served 3.2 million farmers, both directly with a bundle of farm services and indirectly by improving access to farm services in an entire region. In Rwanda, they have co-launched a seed plant to increase the supply of domestic maize seed. In Ethiopia and Malawi, they have partnered with governments and public sector actors to expand local tree planting (Jones & Augustine, 2017).

Figure 9. Contributions of One Acre get Fund (Silvanus et al., 2018)

Farmers who work with One Acre Fund consistently grow larger harvests on the same plot of land compared to their peers, and earn more profit from their farms.

Farmers who work with One Acre Fund consistently grow larger harvests on the same plot of land compared to their peers, and earn more profit from their farms (One Acre Fund, 2022). The farmers helped by the organization are known to increase their farm income by 40%+ per year —from the same plot of land—and produce a surplus for the first time (Jones & Augustine, 2017). Families often invest their extra income in paying school fees for their children. Its estimated that the extra income generated in 2021 funded the equivalent of over 150,000 students attending secondary school for a year (One Acre Fund, 2022). With more income, farmers can accumulate assets that raise their living standards. Assets include investments in their farm, like livestock, and in their home, like solar lights. In 2021, farmers we served directly increased their assets by 20 percent on average (One Acre Fund, 2022). They also grow and buy more nutritious food for their families—like beans, fruit, vegetables, and eggs—which is particularly important for children under the age of two. In 2021, the share of children under the age of two meeting minimum diverse diet standards increased by 12%, with gains particularly pronounced in Rwanda, where our nutrition programming is most developed (Jones & Augustine, 2017).

One Acre Fund farmers have planted 100 million trees to date, and are positioned to plant 1 billion trees total by 2030 since farmers are more likely to enrich their soils with compost and to plant trees alongside their crops, which both capture carbon and build farmers' assets (One Acre Fund,

Beyond soil health improvements, One Acre Fund's training and products generate statistically significant increases in adoption of climate-smart farming practices - including optimal seed choices, insurance products, and crop and asset diversity. One Acre Fund runs multi-year studies of soil fertility, measuring soil organic matter, nutrients, and acidity levels (which allows plants to soak up nutrients). In 2021, One Acre Fund equipped 60,000 farmers to apply agricultural lime, a \$10-20 annual investment per acre that improves the long-term pH balance of acidic soils and can increase crop yields by up to 20-40%. And farmers using our direct services consistently increased carbon in their soil by adding manure and compost. Healthier soils could store up to 20% of current global carbon emissions.

6.2. NOURISH THE CHILDREN

In order to address the issue of childhood malnutrition in a sustainable way, Nourish the Children (NTC) is a project that uses commercial principles. The VitaMeal food, which was created by the nutritional scientists at Nu Skin, serves as the program's first meal (Stephens, 2002). A third-party charitable organization that specializes in providing aid to persons suffering from hunger and famine can receive VitaMeal donations from the company's sales leaders, customers, and staff members (Nu Skin, 2021). More than 700 million meals have been given to hungry kids all over the world since 2002 thanks to Nu Skin and its sales representatives, clients, and staff (Nu Skin, 2021). Distributors receive commissions as with other Nu Skin products (Vun, 2018), and Nu Skin has a smaller profit margin from each sale of VitaMeal than it does from sales of other Nu Skin items (Nu Skin, 2021).

Unlike simple grains with a mostly caloric benefit, VitaMeal is a nutrient-dense food scientifically formulated to meet the nutritional needs of malnourished children (Stephens, 2002). As part of the overall development of VitaMeal, Nu Skin's nutritional scientists determined the ingredients and ratios that were well suited for a malnourished child (Stephens, 2002). The result is a product that provides the essential vitamins and minerals, with a balance of carbohydrates, protein, fat and fibre (Stephens, 2002).

It was found that the Malawian population is accustomed to eating porridge composed with roasted maize (corn) (Ecker, 2010).

Serving Size (128g)			
Serving Per Container 15 (30 Child servings)			
Amount Per Serving			
Calories 480			
Calories from Fat 90			
Calories from Saturated Fat 15			
	% Daily Value		
Total Fat 10g	0.16		
Saturated Fat 1.5g	0.07		
Stearic Acid 0g			
Polyunsaturated Fat 2.5g			
Monounsaturated Fat 2.5g			
Cholesterol 0mg	0		
Sodium 10mg	0		
Potassium 890mg	0.25		
Total Carbohydrates 85g	0.25		
Dietary Fiber 14g	0.56		
Sugars 1g			
Other Carbohydrates 67g			
Protein 16g			
Vitamin A 50%*	Vitamin c 100%*		
Calcium 50%*	Iron 45%*		
Vitamin D 50%*	Vitamin E 120%*		
Vitamin K 50%*	Thiamin 120%*		
Riboflavin 110%*	Niacin 60%*		
Vitamin B ₆ 120%*	Folate 70%*		
Vitamin B ₁₂ 100%*	Biotin 35%*		
Pantothenic Acid 110%*	Phosphorus 70%*		
Iodine 80%*	Magnesium 80%*		
Zinc 70%*	Selenium 100%*		
Copper 70%*	Manganese 120%*		
Chromium 70%*			
*Percent Daily Values are based on a 2,000 calorie diet. Your daily values may be higher or lower depending on your calories needs			
	Calories	2000	2500
Total Fat Less than 65g	80g		
Sat. Fat Less than 20g	25g		
Cholesterol Less than 300mg	300mg		
Sodium Less than 2,400mg	2,400mg		
Total Carbohydrates 300g	375g		
Dietary Fiber 25g	30g		
Calories per gram: fat 9g, carbohydrate 4g, protein 4g			

Figure 10. Nutritional information on VitaMeal (Stephens, 2002)

VitaMeal Roasted Maize & Soya Bean Porridge contains a mix of protein, carbs, calories, and electrolytes in addition to 25 vital vitamins and minerals. Moreover, it contains zinc to treat diarrhoea and vitamin A to prevent the widespread blindness in Africa. It is made specifically to appeal to Malawian kids while providing the best nutrients for malnourished people.

25 vital vitamins and minerals have been added to VitaMeal in highly effective amounts to assist make up for any nutrient shortages and to support healthy growth and development.

Vitamin A is abundant in VitaMeal. The most common cause of blindness in children worldwide is vitamin A deficiency. Xerophthalmia, which affects 125–250 million children in 90 Third World nations, is a major cause of child mortality (Nourish the Children).

Because it aids in ending the vicious cycle of starvation, VitaMeal is exceptional. While standard treatment efforts may offer enough calories and protein, they frequently fall short on the vitamins and minerals necessary to re-establish healthy immunological function (Nourish the Children).

For healthy growth and skeletal development, VitaMeal supplies copious amounts of bone minerals (Ca, Mg, P, Vitamins D and K) (Nourish the Children). High concentrations of essential fatty acids, which are necessary for healthy skin, hair, and nails as well as immunological defence, may be found in VitaMeal. Especially in malnourished children, VitaMeal supplies electrolytes, particularly potassium, that are necessary to maintain appropriate fluid balance and muscular function (Nourish the Children).

Nourish the Children does not come under charity. It is still a social entrepreneurship since it is a business for Nu Skin and distributors like Kipp, who are paid commissions and get credit toward their overall sales quotas for their VitaMeal sales. They also get a non-profit's charitable-donation tax receipt for any VitaMeal purchases they donate to others (Harvard Business Review).

Distributors, or independent salespeople, are essential to multilevel marketers like Nu Skin. The distributors want to make money by purchasing the goods, reselling them to other people, and—more importantly—enticing other distributors to purchase items like VitaMeal. The distributors want to be paid a commission based on how much their new customer's order (Harvard Business Review).

7. CONCLUSION:

Hidden hunger, also known as micronutrient deficiency, is a global issue that affects millions of people, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. First and foremost, micronutrient deficiencies can have severe consequences on human health. They can lead to stunted growth, impaired cognitive development, weakened immune systems, and other health problems. In the long term, these health issues can limit a person's potential, decrease their productivity, and increase their dependence on others for care.

Second, hidden hunger can have a significant impact on a country's economic growth and development. Malnourished individuals are less productive, have lower educational attainment, and are more likely to experience poverty. In the long term, hidden hunger can limit a country's economic potential by reducing the size and quality of its workforce.

While it may seem like an insurmountable problem, hidden hunger is a complex issue that requires a multi-sectoral approach. By working together, the public sector, private sector, social enterprises and NGOs can take concrete steps to address the problem and ensure that all people have access to the vital nutrients they need to lead healthy and productive lives.

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